

ANATOMO-PHYSIOLOGICAL OF THE RESPIRATORY ORGANS
FEATURES AND INSPECTION METHODS, RESPIRATORY ORGANS BASIC
SYMPTOMS OF DISEASES.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6064705>

Ergasheva Nigorxon

Saidova Gulrux

*Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health
named after Abu Ali ibn Sino*

Annotation: *This article is about the development of the respiratory organs when a child is born and the diseases that occur in it.*

Keywords: *respiratory, elements, vessel, nose, throat, newborn, pregnancy.*

The respiratory system is at the beginning of the 4th week of the 3rd week of the fetus formed. The tracheobronchial system is caudal on the endodermal surface of the primary intestine formed as a medial bulge. 4 - By the end of the week the trachea separated from the primary esophagus by the mesenchymal membrane, and then by these two organs branches appear in the middle. The trachea is completely separated from the esophagus. By 5 to 6 weeks the fetus has a firm hand grasp the bronchus is pink. The pink tube is elongated and branched in turn fragmented at 6 weeks of fetal development, segmental and subsegmental at 8-10 weeks bronchi are formed. At 16 weeks the bronchi are formed with the formation of respiratory bronchi tree is formed. By 7 weeks the fetus has a firm hand grasp covered with epithelium, these structural elements are between mesenchymal cells located. The mesenchymal factor is the growth factor of the lungs during the growth of the respiratory system associated with the development of tissue. Bronchi, uncles, connector tissue is formed from the mesenchyme. At 16 weeks the bronchi are empty (recanalization phase), atsinus after 24 weeks develops (alveolar stage). At 10 weeks the carcass in the trachea and bronchi is formed. At 13 weeks the cavities are formed due to the formation of glands in the bronchi is formed. By 13 weeks the epithelial cells of the trachea form mucus-producing cells, which begin to produce mucus by 16 weeks. At this stage, the respiratory system begins to produce airways differentiated. The sections are internal, the airways of the terminal bronchioles Their epithelial layer gradually becomes thinner and in them flickering lashes appear. From 18-19 weeks of pregnancy the detection of the above-mentioned mucus-producing glands increases, and thisBy the end of the week, the goblet cells begin to produce their own secretions. This Another characteristic feature of the period is the intensity of vascular elements proliferation and their entry into the respiratory tract. At 26-28 weeks the lungs, is a period of intensive vascular formation. The lymphatic system of the fetus From 9 to 10 weeks, the lungs are removed from the oral cavity and then the rest formed before birth. Lymph until fetal birth The system is formed mature. New in the broncho-pulmonary system from 7 months of

pregnancy structural unit, i.e. alveoli begin to form, alveoli form gas important in the exchange. It has a high cylindrical epithelium terminal bronchioles, respiratory bronchioles are formed. This is his in turn, it ends with shallow alveolar pathways. Your lungs The morpho-functional unit was still very primitive during this period. Aerogematic barrier in the walls of the alveoli by 8 months of gestation formed. By 8–9 months of gestation, the boronx tree is almost topographical can be formed and only the distal parts of the respiratory system are terminal, Respiratory tract and alveolar sacs are formed, the fetus is born Until then, its lungs are ready for external respiration and gas exchange. Some the degree of formation of the components varies, i.e. its bronchial tree terminal bronchioles. But the functional unit of the lung atsinus and its main part alveoli are now in the formation stage. Alveolar sacs are small, small, flat, extremely rich in blood vessels. Therefore During this period, the walls of the alveoli are thick and small in size. The histological structure of the lungs at birth is the primary physiological atelectasis reminds the state. In newborns, the following segments of the lung are the right lung 1 - (upper extremity,) 2 - (upper back), 9- (basal lateral), 10- (basal posterior) and left Segments 4- (middle lateral), 5 (middle anterior), 6- (basal extremity) of the lung are still mature observed. The respiratory system is divided into 3 parts: 1. Upper respiratory ways (nose, throat). 2. Middle respiratory tract (larynx, larynx, sphincter, segmental bronchi). 3. Lower respiratory tract (bronchioles and alveoli). Upper respiratory tract: (nasal cavity) in newborns small size, narrow nasal passages, lack of lower nasal passages (4 develops with age) and differs from that of adults. Newborn In infants, the nasal cavity is rich in blood and lymphatic vessels. Teary nose The channel is short and relatively wide, its valve apparatus is not well developed There are favorable conditions for the passage of the nasal mucosa. Infection of the conjunctival sac to the nasal cavity in newborns spreads well. In the nasal cavity at night 0.5 g 1 l The bactericidal substance and the fluid containing immunoglobulin A are released. In children With the development of additional cavities during pregnancy due to their small size, their inflammation (gaymaroit, ethmoiditis, frontitis, sinusitis) is rare. Blubber also is a cover that holds in moisture poorly formed, including the arterial type in the nasal cavity underdeveloped, which in turn reduces nosebleeds in first-year children occurs. Cellular tissue develops at the age of 8-9 years. Around the nose There are 4 cavities: frontal, ethmoidal, sphinoidal and maxillary. Gaymor The cavity is formed from the 3rd month of the fetus. It is in newborns appears as an elongated groove. Its size is 8-4-6 mm forms. This is the period of the most intensive growth of the sinus, with permanent swelling of the teeth corresponds to the exit period. Radiologically detected from 3 months, 2-7 development continues until the age of. From 5 to 6 months of age formed. Appears as oval cells in newborns its length is 2-2.5 - 3 mm. The number of cells in this sinus is 5 increases to 7-12 years of age. Ponasimon sinus, the fetus develops at 3 months. Its in newborns length 2-2, 0-1.5 mm, defined as spinoidal diverticula. X-ray diagnosis is 6-7 years old. Its development is 12-15 lasts until the age of. The sinus develops from 4 months of age, 6 By the age of 7, this sinus is rudimentary and begins to grow slowly from the age of 7, and 20 development continues until the age of.

REFERENCES:

[2]

1. O'zME. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000
2. Shopolatov J., Fundamentals of Veterinary Medicine, Tashkent, 1993.
3. T.Umarova, A.Qayumova, M.Ibrohimova. «Hamshiralik ishi». –T.: Abu Ali ibn Sino nomidagi tibbiyot nashriyoti, 2003.

